

Streamlining the optimisation of Sustainable Thermal Energy systems and Prototype technologies in process industries

 Co-funded by the European Union

30 partners 9 countries 48 Months 14.99 M Budget

A photograph of an industrial worker in a dark, protective suit and a yellow hard hat. The worker is standing in a dimly lit industrial environment, possibly a foundry, and is operating a large, cylindrical ladle. Bright, glowing molten metal is being poured from the ladle into a container below. The scene is illuminated by the intense orange and yellow light of the molten metal, creating a high-contrast, dramatic atmosphere. The background shows various industrial structures and pipes.

StreamSTEP aims to transform the management of thermal energy in industrial processes.

The project focuses on waste heat recovery across a broad temperature range, leveraging innovative heat exchanger prototypes and high-temperature heat pumps. To achieve this, StreamSTEP will implement an advanced digital

twinning pipeline, providing the necessary infrastructure for optimization agents to manage energy balance and storage, monitor GHG emissions reductions, and integrate data-driven Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) processes.

TRANSFORM THE MANAGEMENT OF THERMAL ENERGY IN INDUSTRIAL PROCESSES

Advanced Heat Exchangers

High Temperature Heat Pumps

Process industry digitalisation

Improved heat performance

Smart Energy Planning and Management

Our innovative approach is expected to **recover and reuse between 50% and 90% of industrial heat waste**, delivering a payback period of less than three years while enhancing productivity and energy flexibility.

Use Cases

The StreamSTEP system will be demonstrated across five use cases, in

different sectors. The demonstrators will be supported by impact boosting

resources, de-risking the investment and accelerating commercialisation.

TRANSFORM THE MANAGEMENT OF THERMAL ENERGY IN INDUSTRIAL PROCESSES

COPPER

Advanced heat exchangers & HTHPs

Integrating a HPCE prototype of significant scale, supported by a HTHP to maximise the heat recovered from challenging the exhaust stream and upgrading the heat to usable temperature level by end users.

CERAMICS

Multi-sink heat recovery

Recovering high-temperature heat using an advanced heat exchanger, transferring it safely to a thermal oil loop with monitoring to prevent clogging and performance degradation.

SILICON

High density heat exchange

Designing and deploying a Radiative Heat Pipe Basket (RHPB), capable of recovering radiative heat from the product and convective heat from the furnace at a reduced security risk, while also recovering heat from the furnace cooling system.

PLASTICS

Low grade heat valorisation

Implementing the Advanced Heat Pipe Scrubber (AHPS), a new heat exchange system, to recover heat, condense volatiles for safe disposal, reduce treatment costs, and heat water.

OIL AND GAS

Technological feasibility study

Identifying recoverable waste heat, Repsol reuses it in production, reducing reliance on natural gas boilers and imports.

Consortium

TRANSFORM THE MANAGEMENT OF THERMAL ENERGY IN INDUSTRIAL PROCESSES

Expected Impact

Increase energy efficiency for EEs

Reduce investment cost of high temperature installations

Contribute to REPowerEU's climate neutrality and fossil fuel independence goals

Increase process flexibility

Increase competitiveness and resilience of the European process industry

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